

CREATING LEVERAGE TO ENHANCE BIODIVERSITY OUTCOMES
OF GLOBAL BIOMASS TRADE

Biodiversity impact estimates and documentation for indicators on multi-dimensional biodiversity aspects ready for use in WP3

Deliverable 2.3

Summary

Work Package	2
Deliverable N°	2.3
Dissemination Level	ii. Public
Type	i. Demonstrator, Pilot, Prototype
Lead Partner	UFMG
Due Date	December 31, 2023
Submission Date	December 22, 2023
Status	Final
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About CLEVER

Project Number	101060765
Project Title	CLEVER: Creating leverage to enhance biodiversity outcomes of global biomass trade
Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-15
Start date	1 st September 2022
End date	31 st August 2025
Coordinator	RHEINISCHE FRIEDRICH-WILHELMS-UNIVERSITAT BONN

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This project has received funding from the European Research Executive Agency under HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions, grant agreement n°101060765; and from the UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10038491]

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable presents several improvements to the biodiversity models when comparing to the deliverable 2.2. This includes increasing the searches in the random forest models to create the vegetation maps and the biodiversity dimensions, as well as formally testing a new methodology that minimizes the effects of sampling bias on biodiversity estimates. This improvement in the random forest method improved model prediction accuracy for several biodiversity measures, in particular species richness, endemism, and phylogenetic diversity. Furthermore, the use of the new approach to minimize the effects of sampling bias proved to be very effective in generating more realistic results in richness and endemism models. Importantly, we use our models in this deliverable to explore how anthropogenic impact variables were related to decreases in observed biodiversity. This information will be used to derive characterization factors for use in WP6. Specifically, we tested the variables: type of land use (urban areas, croplands, pastures, and native vegetation), cropland intensity, intensity of cattle harvesting and number of fire events. The results presented here represent an important advancement in biodiversity models by allowing predictions that are less influenced by sampling bias and more accurate. These results provide a valuable further step in describing human-induced changes in vegetation and biodiversity patterns across both South America and Africa. Factors such as croplands, livestock pastures and the intensity of these land uses are significantly related to biodiversity loss. The biodiversity impact estimates, and the documentation provided in this deliverable will provide direct inputs in upcoming CLEVER work in WP3 and WP6.

INTRODUCTION

One of the main drivers of global biodiversity loss is habitat loss due to the conversion of natural ecosystems, typically associated to agricultural expansion^{1,2}. Thus, it is critical to understand the impacts of anthropogenic drivers associated with biodiversity loss. Agriculture and livestock are fundamental activities for human subsistence, but they have significant impacts on biodiversity. These practices, especially when intensive, can lead to the loss of natural habitats, alteration of ecosystems, and reduction in species diversity. However, quantifying the impacts on biodiversity is not a simple task, as accurately measuring the effects of agriculture and livestock in different contexts and geographical scales can be a substantial challenge.

One of the major challenges in quantifying these impacts on biodiversity is accounting for the effect of sampling bias³⁻⁶. Sampling bias arises due to the higher sampling density along more accessible areas (near roads, rivers, or trails), as well as samples collected for more visible or charismatic species⁶⁻⁹. This bias is particularly pronounced in the tropics, which also host the largest share of global biodiversity^{6,10}. Failing to account for this bias can result in a misrepresentation species distribution and abundance, which influences perceived patterns of biodiversity and can hence limit our ability to make well-informed decisions for biodiversity conservation⁶⁻⁹. In this regard, various methods have been developed to mitigate the effects of incomplete or biased sampling campaigns¹¹⁻¹³. Among these methods, species distribution models (SDMs) stand out. SDMs use georeferenced information of species occurrences together with environmental predictors to infer the potential species distributions in unsampled areas^{14,15}. Besides, spatial interpolation is also useful to estimate spatial variations of biodiversity dimensions (e.g., richness, endemism, beta-diversity). For example, spatial interpolation through kriging employs spatial autocorrelation to fill in the sampling gaps, producing continuous surfaces of biodiversity dimensions as a result¹⁶⁻¹⁸. Another promising approach is the use of predictive models that use environmental variables as inputs and machine learning techniques to estimate biodiversity dimensions where sampling data are scarce. Predictive models are analogous to SDMs but, in addition to species distribution, they can also predict other biodiversity metrics such as richness, endemism, and beta-diversity^{16,17,19}.

In the first part of this report, we present a new methodology that tests and quantifies the effects of sampling bias on biodiversity estimates. Based on these results, in the second part of our results, we estimate biodiversity losses (while using the above methods to account for sampling bias) in South America and Africa. Specifically, we present the estimated impacts of agriculture and livestock (and their different levels of intensity), on biodiversity losses or change. This approach has the potential to generate predictions under various future scenarios including agricultural expansion, intensification, climate change, and deforestation.

OBJECTIVES

The objective of this study was to improve the biodiversity models presented in D2.2 through new methodologies that consider the sampling effort in the estimation of biodiversity and to estimate the impacts of land use and intensity of agricultural use on biodiversity loss in South America and Africa. Through this, we intend to provide the inputs needed for further CLEVER work in WP3 and WP6.

METHODS

We developed and tested a new methodology to model biodiversity while reducing the effects of sampling bias on estimates of richness and endemism. Here, we summarize the findings from incorporating this method into the biodiversity models (find the complete analysis in the annex, which has been submitted for publication and approved in April 2024).

Novel approach: incorporating sampling effort for modeling biodiversity.

Regressions, heuristic models, and machine learning approaches use diverse methodologies to estimate the influence of predictor variables on the dependent variable. Given the strong evidence linking biodiversity estimated patterns and the sampling effort, incorporating the sampling effort as a predictor variable should be a promising strategy. Therefore, we propose that sampling effort be included as a predictor variable, regardless of the algorithm employed. After training the models for projection purposes, the sampling effort variable is replaced by a uniform surface with a constant value representing the maximum sampling density estimated using a 50 km radius kernel function. In this way, the models will estimate the biodiversity patterns as a function of environmental predictor variables plus the collection effort. This approach, called Uniform Sampling from Sampling Effort (USSE), can be applied to predict any biodiversity metric (richness, endemism, beta-diversity, phylogenetic diversity, etc.) as well as with any prediction algorithm (GLM, GDM, GAM, Random Forest, Neural Networks, etc.). To model species richness based on USSE, we trained the same three algorithms: Generalized Linear Models (GLM), Multivariate Adaptive Regression Spline (MARS), and Random Forest (RF).

Validation of new approach

To test the methods with respect to their predictive capacity for each biodiversity metric (species richness, endemism, and beta-diversity), we applied a correlation test between the estimated values and those obtained directly from the experimental control (simulated maps of species distribution (see annex, under review)). We compared the results from all methods for modeling the selected biodiversity metrics with the frequency distributions of the 100 repetitions for each scenario (25, 50, 75, 100, and random) (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Species richness models with simulated data and their relationship with sampling bias. **A**: environmental predictor variable (1st PCA axis); **B**: species richness measured directly from the simulated maps of species distribution under scenarios 25, 50, 75, 100; **C**: the accessibility map; and **D**: correlation between species richness measured directly from the simulated maps of species distribution under scenarios 25, 50, 75, and 100 and the accessibility map.

Biodiversity Models

We improved the biodiversity models through the use of our new approach (described above, see annex for paper under revision) and by increasing the number of trees in the random forest algorithm, from 500 to 1000. As the optimization of the random forest algorithm is closely related to the number of trees used in its search, increasing the number of trees, in general, generates improvements in the predictions of this algorithm²⁰.

Effect of Land Use on Biodiversity Loss

To test the effects of different land uses as well as the intensity of agriculture- and livestock-use, we used a generalized linear model. For this, we used as a dependent variable each of the dimensions of biodiversity modeled. As predictor variables, we used: 1 - types of land use²¹, 2 - country, 3 - ecoregions²², 4 - number of cattle heads/km²²³, 5 - percentage of agricultural area in 0.025° pixels²⁴. As samples, equidistant points (5km) throughout the study area were used. Countries and ecoregions were included as predictor variables only to function as a control for variation in the samples. To choose the databases for land use, livestock, and croplands, we used as criteria the scope of the data, which should cover South America and Africa, the quality of the data source, and the methods applied to map the data. Other data sources can also be used in future analyses to provide a clearer idea of the effect of these sources on the results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Novel approach: incorporating sampling effort for modeling biodiversity

For modelling species richness, the USSE approach attained the predictive capability of $r = 0.85$ and $r = 0.96$ (Pearson correlation) in the scenarios, in which occurrences were concentrated in regions far from access routes and otherwise, respectively. In addition, the USSE method yielded a lower dispersion in all methods and for all modeled scenarios, hence being significantly better than the other methods ($p < 0.05$ in GLM test) (Figure 2A). Prediction based only on the environmental variable achieved the second-best result ($r = 0.40$ and $r = 0.88$) with respect to scenarios of occurrences near and away from access routes, respectively). The results of this method had the highest dispersion (0.05 to 0.20), indicating a highly dependency on the spatial distribution of species (Figure 2A). Spatial interpolation yielded lower results than those of environmental variable prediction ($r = 0.23$ and $r = 0.78$ for scenarios near and away from access routes, respectively) and was not significantly different from the previous method for all modeled scenarios (Figure 2A). SDMs yielded the lowest predictive capacity for species richness ($r = 0.16$ and $r = 0.46$ for scenarios near and away from access routes, respectively), and were significantly different from the other methods, except for spatial interpolation under the 50 and 75 species distribution scenarios and from the environmental prediction method under the 50 scenarios. For modelling endemism, all methods yielded similar results, without statistically significant differences, ($r = 0.49$ to 0.77) (Figure 4B). For beta-diversity, environmental prediction with and without USSE yielded very similar results (Figure 2C), without statistically significant differences. USSE did not improve GDM results ($r = 0.80$ to 0.96) (Figure 2C). The SCI interpolation was significantly worse than GDM, with low predictive capacity ($r = 0.22$ to 0.38). Sampling size had little impact on all methods. GDM's internal metric of 62.04% explaining deviance in fact underestimates its predictive capacity ($> 80\%$), as pointed out from the correlation with Beta-diversity directly measured from the simulated maps of species distribution. The USSE approach represents a major advance for biodiversity modeling by incorporating sampling bias directly into the models, minimizing prediction errors caused by sampling differences between areas.

Figure 2: Pearson correlation (r) between the estimated biodiversity dimensions. **(A)** species richness, **(B)** endemism, and **(C)** beta-diversity) from each method under the modeled scenarios and those directly measured from the simulated maps of species distribution. Species Distribution Models (SDM); Spatial Interpolation (SI); Environmental Prediction (EP); Environmental Prediction with Uniform Sampling from Sampling Effort (USSE). Frequency from 100 replicas of each species distribution scenario. The USSE approach outperformed the other methods in predicting species richness, and was similar to the other methods in estimating endemism and beta-diversity.

Biodiversity model

The biodiversity models showed an improvement in predictive capacity with the increase in the number of trees in the Random Forest model. The Random Forest model to estimate endemism ($R^2=0.79$), species richness ($R^2=0.85$), and phylodiversity ($R^2=0.74$) demonstrated the best predictions than the previous model (**Figure 2-4**).

Endemicity

Figure 2. Endemicity model: **A:** Baseline of endemism; **B:** Current endemism; **C:** Current reduction of endemism in percentage of change, in relation to the baseline.

Species richness

Figure 3. Species richness model. **A:** Baseline of species richness; **B:** Current species richness; **C:** Current reduction of species richness in number of species, in relation to the baseline.

Phylodiversity

Figure 4. Phylodiversity model. **A:** Baseline of phylodiversity; **B:** Current phylodiversity; **C:** Current reduction of phylodiversity in number of species, in relation to the baseline.

Impact of Land Use on Biodiversity Loss

In all tests, the types of land use, number of cattle heads/km² and percentage of agricultural area in 0.025° pixels were significantly related to the reduction in species richness, endemism, species composition, and phylodiversity ($p < 0.05$). The only land-use not significantly related to the reduction in the number of species was urban land-use, which is expected due to small extension of these areas in the studied landscape. Most countries, biomes and ecoregions presented results significantly related to the reduction in the analysed dimensions of biodiversity (Annex). The intensity of use by croplands or cattle, and fire, also showed a significant relationship with the reduction of biodiversity in all dimensions evaluated. Croplands and pasture areas present the greatest magnitudes of isolated biodiversity loss (**Figure 5**).

Figure 5. Magnitude of the isolated impact of land uses and intensity of cattle and croplands. **A:** land use in the reduction of species richness, **B:** in endemicity and **C:** in species composition; **D:** in phylodiversity; **E:** intensity of Cattle in reduction of species richness, **F:** in endemicity, **G:** species composition and **H:** in phylodiversity; **I:** intensity of Cropland in reduction of species richness, **J:** in endemicity, **K:** species composition and **L:** in phylodiversity; Asterix indicates statistical significance ($p < 0.05$)

Limitations and future research

In summary, random forest models showed superior performance in predicting endemism, phylodiversity, and species richness, as compared to all other algorithms tested. This underscores the value of advanced modelling techniques in biodiversity research; although such modelling approaches still have limitations such as overfitting. In simulations, our new approach to minimizing the effects of collection bias on biodiversity model predictions proved effective for richness and endemism. For beta diversity, this approach proved unnecessary, since the GDM technique, used to model beta diversity, can already deal well with collection bias. Another limitation related to the vegetation model is the inability to generate temporal data for other periods (based on satellite images), which would allow for the creation of even more precise vegetation models with temporary training. We have reached out to the researchers who produced this data to explore the possibility of using their model to predict canopy height data for other time periods; however, we have yet to receive a response regarding this possibility. Future modelling efforts may benefit from testing more complex methods such as deep neural networks, which likely require more computational effort and processing time.

In sum, our results help identify regions where species richness, endemism, phylodiversity, and overall change in patterns and composition has been impacted by different land-uses and their intensities in both South America and Africa. This mapping of biodiversity impacts, and the included documentation, provides critical inputs for future CLEVER work as well as broader biodiversity research in these regions.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, we have been able to improve biodiversity models and identify how anthropogenic factors are related to biodiversity loss in South America and Africa. By identifying regions of high priority for conservation and areas experiencing significant change and declines in biodiversity, our study contributes to the knowledge base required for sustainable and targeted conservation actions in these ecologically significant regions. With this novel approach, we were able to significantly reduce the effects of sampling bias in species richness models. We have also estimated the impacts of land-use change on different dimensions of biodiversity, at different levels of agricultural intensification, which indicated a significant association between biodiversity loss and cropland and pastures. Likewise, intensity of use and fire are related to loss of biodiversity. Future improvements also include to building models for future impacts (e.g., the effects of climate change, land-use change, and fire).

PROJECT OUTPUTS ACHIEVED

With these modelling efforts, we have generated a second version of several biodiversity indicators (available and updated at Zenodo (DOI: 12749084 and 8305248), and quantified their impacts. The results will be used as input for future CLEVER quantitative frameworks that aim to analyze agricultural supply-chains, agri-environmental policies, and related governance mechanisms.

Specifically, these modelled outputs represent a basis for upcoming developments (i.e., models of future impacts, species abundance models), which will directly inform and improve the research of WP3, WP6 and WP7, including life-cycle analyses and integrated assessment models aiming to estimate biodiversity impacts of different trade-flows.

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ANNEX

Controlling the Effects of Sampling Bias in Biodiversity Models

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Abstract

Aim

Sampling bias and gaps have a direct influence on the perceived patterns of biodiversity, hence limiting our ability to make well-informed decisions about biodiversity conservation. Yet most biodiversity methods either disregard or underestimate the effect of sampling bias and gaps in modeling biodiversity patterns. Thus, our objective is to test the sensitivity of commonly used models to sampling bias and collection gaps for predicting biodiversity dimensions (richness, endemism, and beta-diversity) and introducing a novel approach that employs the sampling effort to minimize the effects of collection bias and gaps in biodiversity models.

Location

South America

Methods

Here, we use controlled simulations of virtual species distribution and sampling effort to test the sensitivity of commonly used methods—species distribution models (SDMs), spatial interpolation (SI), and environmental prediction (EP)—to sampling bias and collection gaps for estimating species richness, endemism, and beta-diversity. Our research contributes to advancing biodiversity modeling by introducing a novel approach, named USSE, that employs the sampling effort to minimize the effects of collection bias and gaps.

Results and Main conclusions

EP with USSE has proven effective in accurately predicting species richness, especially in scenarios in which the sampling effort does not coincide with

biodiversity niches. It outperformed SI and SDMs. The latter performed poorly, yielding the lowest predictive score. In estimating endemism and beta-diversity, all methods yielded similar results, without statistically significant differences. For estimating beta-diversity, the Generalized Dissimilarity Model proved to be a robust method, even in face of biased sampling. Controlled simulations are key to testing biodiversity methods. These tests can isolate confounding factors inherent to real-world data, enabling robust methodological assessments. Although fieldwork and curation of collections must remain indispensable, novel biodiversity methods could help overcome the limitations of sampling biases, helping as a result expedite the bold conservation actions much needed.

Keywords: sampling bias, modeling, SDM, GDM, biodiversity, simulation

Introduction

Modeling biodiversity distribution is key to understanding and conserving ecosystems. Yet this is challenging due to large sampling gaps and collection bias present in biodiversity datasets (Hoveka et al., 2020; Monsarrat et al., 2019; Oliveira et al., 2016; Sporbert et al., 2019). This bias arises due to the concentration of collection efforts in specific areas or on more visible species (Meineke & Daru, 2021; Oliveira et al., 2016; Vale & Jenkins, 2012; Williams & Pearson, 2019). One of the main factors contributing to collection bias is the concentration of sampling in more accessible areas near roads, rivers, or trails. (Oliveira et al., 2016). And this effect is particularly notable in tropical regions, which house the largest share of biodiversity (Engemann et al., 2015; Oliveira et al., 2016).

Collection bias has a direct influence on the perceived patterns of biodiversity (Engemann et al., 2015; Oliveira et al., 2016), usually misrepresenting species distribution and abundance, hence limiting our ability to make well-informed decisions about biodiversity conservation (Meineke & Daru, 2021; Oliveira et al., 2016; Vale & Jenkins, 2012; Williams & Pearson, 2019). For example, sampling bias can lead us to mistakenly believe that areas more frequently studied are more biodiverse than others (Oliveira et al., 2016). Additionally, some biodiversity patterns, such as species richness, are intrinsically linked to the quality and scope of the samples collected, making them particularly sensitive to sampling bias (Engemann et al., 2015; Oliveira et al., 2016). While patterns of endemism and beta-diversity may be less affected by sampling bias than richness patterns, no aspect of biodiversity remains completely unaffected by insufficient or biased sampling (Oliveira et al., 2016). In biodiversity studies, it is crucial therefore to acknowledge that collected samples may provide an inaccurate representation of the geographic biodiversity patterns, given that the most biodiverse regions are often difficult to access and, consequently, less sampled (Engemann et al., 2015; Oliveira et al., 2016; Pelz & Luebbers, 1998). Overcoming this data constraint

through adequate sampling is not a simple task, requiring considerable resources and time, which are seldom available. In view of this fact, modelers must attempt to develop methods that mitigate sampling shortfalls in order to attain a comprehensive assessment of biodiversity patterns.

In this regard, various methods have been developed to mitigate the effects of incomplete or biased sampling campaigns (Galante et al., 2018; Moua et al., 2020; Pelz & Luebbers, 1998). Among these methods, species distribution models (SDMs) stand out. SDMs use georeferenced information of species occurrences together with environmental predictors to infer the potential species distributions in unsampled areas (Elith & Leathwick, 2009; Guisan & Thuiller, 2005). In turn, spatial interpolation is also useful to estimate spatial variations of biodiversity dimensions (e.g., richness, endemism, beta-diversity). For example, spatial interpolation through kriging employs spatial autocorrelation to fill in the sampling gaps, producing as a result continuous surfaces of biodiversity dimensions (Alves et al., 2020; Hortal & Lobo, 2011; Oliveira et al., 2019). Predictive models, having as input environmental variables, consist of another promising approach that may employ machine learning techniques to estimate biodiversity dimensions where sampling data are scarce. They are analogous to SDMs but can also predict, in addition to species distribution, biodiversity metrics, such as richness, endemism, and beta-diversity (Ferrier et al., 2007; Hortal & Lobo, 2011; Oliveira et al., 2019).

Another challenge is that sampling gaps and collection bias impose significant limitations to the validation of biodiversity models, regardless of the methods, since inadequate sampling may result in overestimation of the models' predictive ability (Lobo et al., 2008; Palmer et al., 2008). Therefore, there is indeed a need to test the sensitivity of mostly used biodiversity modeling methods with respect to sampling bias and gaps so as to develop new approaches that could help minimize these effects. This is crucial for investigating and testing biogeographic and macroecological hypotheses, as well as for devising sound policies aimed at mitigating the impacts of climate and land use changes on biodiversity loss.

Yet to assess the effect of sampling bias on biodiversity modeling methods (SDM, interpolation, predictive models, etc), we cannot use actual data on species occurrence due to sampling incompleteness. One common recourse is to rely on simulations of virtual species distributions and synthetic sampling. This sort of controlled experiment allows us to create experimental designs that would be impossible to find in the real world (De Marco & Nóbrega, 2018; Garzon-Lopez et al., 2016; Grimmer et al., 2021; Meynard et al., 2019). As a result, we would be able to ascertain the capacity of the models at predicting species distribution since we know the correct answer beforehand (Grimmett et al., 2021; Meynard et al., 2019). Moreover, simulations are instrumental in investigating the effects of model parameters and algorithms, regardless of the biodiversity predictive

model in question (Miller, 2014), given that we have control over the assumptions of the simulated scenarios, thereby creating pseudo-experiments in which even the effects of random variations can be measured. Furthermore, simulations enable the rigorous testing of different methods under wide-ranging conditions, from highly favorable sampling scenarios to challenging contexts in which the methods might be more prone to erroneous responses. Here, we explore these possibilities with the objective of testing the sensitivity of commonly used models to sampling bias and collection gaps for predicting biodiversity dimensions (richness, endemism, and beta-diversity). Our research contributes to advancing biodiversity modeling by introducing a novel approach that employs the sampling effort as a way to minimize the effects of collection bias and gaps.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

We selected a rectangular study area in South America ($-70^{\circ}.02$, $-22^{\circ}.15$: $-40^{\circ}.94$, $-3^{\circ}.40$) that could encompass the largest possible land extent, but coastal areas, to capture a wide-range of environmental condition so as to simulate the most diversity of habitats. The environmental conditions were summarized by using a principal component analysis (PCA). Variables include 1) Annual Mean Temperature, 2) Mean Diurnal Range, 3) Isothermality, 4) Temperature Seasonality, 5) Max Temperature of Warmest Month, 6) Mean Temperature of Coldest Month, 7) Annual Temperature Range, 8) Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter, 9) Mean Temperature of Driest Quarter, 10) Mean Temperature of Warmest Quarter, 11) Mean Temperature of Coldest Quarter, 12) Annual Precipitation, 13) Precipitation of Wettest Month, 14) Precipitation of Driest Month, 15) Precipitation Seasonality, 16) Precipitation of Wettest Quarter, 17) Precipitation of Driest Quarter, 18) Precipitation of Warmest Quarter, and 19) Precipitation of Coldest Quarter (all variables from <https://www.worldclim.org>). We selected the first PCA axis (79.3% of the variation) as the sole environmental predictor in order to simplify the simulations of species distributions.

Virtual Distributions of Species

To create the virtual distribution of species, we started with a few assumptions: 1 – the distribution is determined by the population size (areas with more than one individual of the species), which, in turn, is determined by the 2 - likelihood of the species occurring given the environmental condition. In this manner, we assume that the distribution is directly related to the species' niche, i.e., to the most suitable conditions for the occurrence of viable species populations. To simulate species niches, we used normal probability distribution functions (PDF) defined by the means and standard deviations of the environmental condition (the first PCA axis) representing a set of virtual species' niches. In this way, places with conditions more favorable to the species occurrence (close to the mean PDF

value) have a higher probability of finding a species occurrence. To convert this probability into population size, we use a multiplication factor, which determines how many individuals of the species can occur at a given probability value. To make this parameter realistic, embracing both abundant and rare species, the population multiplier is a number (between 100 and 1000), randomly selected for each virtual species. In addition, binary maps of presence and absence are generated for each simulated species distribution.

Species Occurrence Sampling

To replicate realistic sampling patterns that commonly have bias because of the tendency of collecting near access routes (Oliveira et al., 2016) and the higher chance of abundant species being sampled, we used two sampling rules: 1 – to replicate the conspicuousness bias (abundant species are frequently more sampled), we established a threshold value (number of individuals) required for a species to be detected and hence sampled at a specific location (raster cell of 25 km²). To do so, we drew a value between zero and the highest number of individuals on the simulated map of the species' population. If the analyzed cell holds a number of individuals greater than the drawn value, a second rule determines whether the cell occurrences will be sampled or not upon a sampling PDF derived by using a normal distribution as a function of distance to access routes (Weiss et al., 2018). As a result, the number of sampled occurrences for each species depends on how abundant it is and how close these occurrences are to access routes plus a randomness component. The sampling method resulted in some species not having any recorded occurrence, which in our modeling would represent unknown species, adding more realism to our approach. To test the effect of the sampling size on the representation of the biodiversity dimensions, the total number of recorded occurrences for each species was used for modeling biodiversity in the various methods tested. Then we tested the same methods using only 50% of recorded occurrences selected at random.

Simulation of species distribution scenarios

To test the performance of different methods in predicting biodiversity spatial patterns, we constructed four scenarios based on species' environmental preferences. These scenarios were designed to include from favorable sampling conditions for good prediction (where the collection bias interferes less with the results) to less favorable ones (in which collection bias truly hinders the representation of biodiversity patterns). Because the spatial concentration of species directly affects species richness, endemism, and beta diversity, we designed four scenarios, each one with different levels of correlation between accessibility (access route map) and the sum of species per cell. For each scenario we simulated the distribution of 1,000 species, centering their PDFs on

a specific value of 1st PCA axis, i.e., 100, 75, 50, and 25, which would represent the most suitable occurrence condition for those species. In this way, most species distribution simulated under a given scenario would occupy similar geographic niches, which is analogous to nature, where more species occur in the tropics. We repeated each scenario 100 times through independent simulations.

We then built an additional random scenario in which the species distribution does not concentrate within any specific environmental condition. This scenario serves as a null model to test the prediction ability of biodiversity methods when there is no environmental control. Access routes are concentrated in the southeast portion of the study area, which coincides with low values of the environmental variable (Figure 1B and D). The coincidence between sampling effort and species niches facilitates a more accurate prediction of biodiversity dimensions since, in this case, the collection bias does not interfere much with what would be a representative sampling of those species.

Novel approach: incorporating sampling effort for modeling biodiversity

Species richness models

Species richness is a function of the number of species, so it tends to be highly correlated with collection intensity (Oliveira et al., 2016). Since there are several methods that estimate species richness by attempting to reduce the sampling effects, we tested four methods: 1) Species distribution models (SDM) that estimate species richness by summing the individual models of species distribution (Yang et al., 2013); 2) Spatial interpolation of species richness by using kriging (Hortal & Lobo, 2011); 3) Prediction of species richness using environmental variables (Hortal & Lobo, 2011); 4) finally, the latter model, now with the inclusion of the sampling effort as a predictive variable.

- 1) For the species distribution models (SDM), we employed an ensemble of six algorithms: Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Generalized Boosted models (GBM), Generalized Linear Models (GLM), Multivariate Adaptive Regression Spline (MARS), Maxent, and Random Forest (RF). The ensemble is obtained by averaging the results from the six algorithms, which are weighted using their validation score as defined by the Area Under the Curve (AUC). Each algorithm used 75% of the sampled data for training and 25% for validation. Since the SDMs generate probability or suitability maps for species occurrences, we used the maximum proportion of correct predictions as the threshold to convert these maps into binary ones before getting the final sum of species distribution (Elith & Leathwick, 2009). For methods that require absence data, we used 100 pseudo-absences.

- 2) We used Gaussian kriging to spatially interpolate species richness. Richness data were estimated using as a partition hexagons with a 100 km radius.
- 3) To model species richness using environmental variables as predictors, we tested three algorithms: Generalized Linear Models (GLM), Multivariate Adaptive Regression Spline (MARS), and Random Forest (RF). As the dependent variable, we used the richness measured at the centroid of hexagons with a 100 km radius. We used the 1st PCA axis as the predictor variable. The GLM applies a Gaussian fitting function, and the RF employs 500 trees. We selected the best algorithm using the correlation between the algorithm prediction and the richness values obtained directly by summing the simulated maps of species distribution because the best model is expected to yield the highest correlation with the simulated control.
- 4) Here, we introduce a new methodological approach, Uniform Sampling from Sampling Effort (USSE). Regressions, heuristic models, and machine learning approaches use diverse methodologies to estimate the influence of predictor variables on the dependent variable. Given the strong evidence linking biodiversity estimated patterns and the sampling effort, incorporating the sampling effort as a predictor variable should be a promising strategy. So, we propose that sampling effort be included as a predictor variable, regardless of the algorithm employed. After training the models, for projection purposes, the sampling effort variable is replaced with a uniform surface with a constant value representing the maximum sampling density estimated using a 50 km radius kernel function. In this way, the models will estimate the biodiversity patterns as a function of environmental predictor variables plus the collection effort. This approach can be applied to predict any biodiversity metric (richness, endemism, beta-diversity, phylogenetic diversity, etc.) and also be used with any prediction algorithm (GLM, GDM, GAM, Random Forest, Neural Networks, etc.). To model species richness based on USSE, we trained the same three algorithms: Generalized Linear Models (GLM), Multivariate Adaptive Regression Spline (MARS), and Random Forest (RF).

Endemicity models

Endemicity was estimated using the endemism weighted index corrected for species richness, as this index is less influenced by sampling effort (Oliveira et al., 2016). As there are several methods to estimate endemism in poorly sampled areas that attempt to reduce the effects of sampling bias, we tested three methods here: 1) Spatial interpolation of endemism using kriging; 2) Prediction using environmental variable; 3) Prediction using environmental variable based on the USSE methodology. To spatially interpolate endemism, we used the

Gaussian kriging as described above. For environmental prediction, we tested the same three algorithms again: Generalized Linear Models (GLM), Multivariate Adaptive Regression Spline (MARS), and Random Forest (RF). The dependent variable in the models is the endemism calculated for the centroid of the 100 km radius hexagons. The GLM uses a Gaussian distribution function and, in turn, the RF uses 500 trees. We selected the best algorithm based on the correlation between the results of each prediction algorithm and the endemism obtained directly from the simulated maps of species distribution. We used the same methodology described above to model endemism based on the USSE approach.

Beta-diversity models

Beta-diversity was estimated using the Bray-Curtis index (Bray & Curtis, 1957). To generate maps of the spatial variations in species composition, we tested three approaches: 1 – Species Composition Interpolation (SCI) (Oliveira et al., 2017), 2 – Generalized Dissimilarity Model (GDM) (Ferrier et al., 2007), using only the environmental variable as the predictor, 3 – GDM using both the environmental variable and the USSE approach. To estimate compositional variation using the SCI method, we ran 1000 rounds of Non-metric Multidimensional Scaling (NMDS) and interpolated results by Gaussian kriging. In the GDM method, we used hexagons with a 100 km radius as the sampling unit, equal type weighting, and three I-splines for model fitting. As a predictor variable, we used only the first PCA axis in one test, and in another, we included the USSE approach.

Validation

To test the methods with respect to their predictive capacity for each biodiversity metric (species richness, endemism, and beta-diversity), we applied a correlation test between the estimated values and those obtained directly from the experimental control (simulated maps of species distribution). We compared the results from all methods for modeling the selected biodiversity metrics with the frequency distributions of the 100 repetitions for each scenario (25, 50, 75, 100, and random) (Figure 1). We used a generalized linear model (GLM) with a Poisson function to check for statistically significant differences between the results of the biodiversity estimation methods under the species distribution scenarios.

Sensitivity Test of Biodiversity Distribution Modeling Methods with respect to Sample Bias

To test how sensitive the different methods are to sample bias, we performed a linear regression between the simulated maps of species distribution (experimental control) and the sampling density estimated with a 50 km radius kernel, as well as between the latter and the biodiversity metric estimates from

the various methods. Additionally, we correlated the metrics directly measured at the centroids of 100 km radius hexagons with the sampling effort to test whether there is a relationship between the biodiversity patterns in the simulated maps and the sampling effort. This procedure helps us determine if our simulated control represents the common spatial patterns obtained from biological collection data (Oliveira et al., 2016).

Results

Virtual Species Distributions

The simulated maps of species distributions exhibit a wide variation of abundance and geographic amplitude. Our artificial sampling approach closely replicates the commonly observed sampling patterns in the real world, with a few species having many records and the majority presenting only a few records (Oliveira et al., 2016). In all scenarios of species distribution, there are species without occurrence, replicating unknown species in the real world (ranging from 2.5% to 5.7% of the simulated distributions). Species known by only one occurrence range from 4% to 64%, varying according to the center PDF value for the environmental suitability of each scenario.

Simulation of Species Distribution Scenarios

The relationship between species richness obtained from the simulated maps and the accessibility index indicates that the modeled scenarios represent different degrees of difficulty for making accurate predictions (Figure 1E). The random scenario met the premise of representing a control case encompassing a wide variation in the geographic concentration of species in various environmental conditions.

Species Richness Models

On average, the MARS algorithm yielded the best predictive capability (Pearson's $r = 0.94$). This algorithm with the USSE approach attained the predictive capability of $r = 0.85$ and $r = 0.96$ (Pearson correlation) in the scenarios, in which occurrences were concentrated in regions far from access routes and otherwise, respectively. In addition, the USSE method yielded a lower dispersion in all methods and for all modeled scenarios, hence being significantly better than the other methods ($p < 0.05$) (Figure 1A). Prediction based only on the environmental variable achieved the second-best result ($r = 0.40$ and $r = 0.88$) with respect to scenarios of occurrences near and away from access routes, respectively). It was also significantly different from the results of the other methods ($p < 0.05$) except for the spatial interpolation in all scenarios (Figure 1A). The results of this method had the highest dispersion (0.05 to 0.20), indicating a highly dependency on the spatial distribution of species (Figure 1A). Spatial interpolation yielded lower results than those of environmental variable prediction ($r = 0.23$ and $r = 0.78$ in

scenarios near and away from access routes, respectively) and was not significantly different from the previous method for all modeled scenarios (Figure 1A. SDMs yielded the lowest predictive capacity for species richness ($r = 0.16$ and $r = 0.46$ in scenarios near and away from access routes, respectively), and were significantly different from the other methods, except for spatial interpolation under the 50 and 75 species distribution scenarios and from the environmental prediction method under the 50 scenario. Still, the mean AUC of the SDM methods for individual species distribution was high (0.90), with the best result attained by using Maxent (0.96).

Regarding the effect of sampling size, SDMs exhibited the highest variation in predictive capability, reducing the r metric by up to 16% in the scenario with half the number of samples. Also, prediction based solely on environmental variables showed a high variation (reduction in r of up to 12%), demonstrating its highly sensitive to sampling size. On the other hand, spatial interpolation showed the lowest variation in predictive capability, followed by the environmental prediction method with USSE, hence suggesting little sensitive to sampling size.

Endemicity model

On average, Random Forest (RF) attained the best predictive capacity ($r=0.69$, average of 100 replicas). All methods yielded similar results, without statistically significant differences, ($r=0.49$ to 0.77) (Figure 2A) and sampling size had little impact whatever the method.

Beta-diversity models

In all modeled scenarios (including the random one), environmental prediction with and without USSE yielded very similar results (Figure 2B), without statistically significant differences. USSE did not improve GDM results ($r=0.80$ to 0.96) (Figure 2B). The SCI interpolation was significantly worse than GDM, with low predictive capacity ($r=0.22$ to 0.38) (Figure 2B). Sampling size had little impact on all methods. GDM's internal metric of 62.04% explaining deviance in fact underestimates its predictive capacity ($> 80\%$), as pointed out from the correlation with Beta-diversity directly measured from the simulated maps of species distribution.

Test of Relationship between Sampling Effort and biodiversity modeling methods

The relationship between species richness measured directly from the simulated maps of species distribution and the sampling effort was negligible (linear regression $R^2=0.007$), whereas the relationship between species richness measured using hexagons and sampling effort was high ($R^2=0.93$) (Figure 3). USSE reduced the effects of sampling bias in estimating species richness, yielding results similar to those measured directly from the simulated maps of species distribution ($R^2=0.008$). The second-best method for mitigating sampling

bias in species richness estimation was environmental prediction ($R^2=0.09$). In contrast, SDM and spatial interpolation reduced only slightly sampling bias ($R^2=0.53$ and 0.56 , respectively) (Figure 3). Sampling bias had very little influence on both endemism and beta-diversity as estimated by the tested methods (Figures 4 and 5).

Discussion

Species richness predicted by using environmental variables with the USSE approach closely approximates those obtained directly from the maps of simulated species distribution, making it therefore an effective approach for estimating species richness, even in the cases in which the sampling effort does not coincide with the species niches. Furthermore, its ability to estimate richness remains robust even if most of the species have few records, and many remain unknown (almost 6%). A notable advantage of this method is its adaptability, as it can be applied in conjunction with a wide range of prediction algorithms for modeling species richness as well as other biodiversity metrics, such as phylogenetic and functional diversity. USSE, thus, opens the possibility to improve various algorithms, from regression-based approaches (GLM, GAM, and SAR), to heuristic ones, such as genetic algorithms, Random Forest, and machine learning techniques, including neural networks. Spatial interpolation had significant limitation in predicting species richness, with a noticeable loss of effectiveness in challenging species distribution scenarios strongly affected by sampling bias.

Species Distribution Models (SDMs), on the other hand, performed poorly at estimating species richness in scenarios in which sampling effort deviates from the species niches. This limitation may be attributed to the accumulation of errors associated with the estimates of individual species distribution (Grenié et al., 2020). Moreover, the results of SDMs are strongly influenced by sampling size and sampling biases (Bean et al., 2012; Hanberry et al., 2012; Wisz et al., 2008), and such errors tend to mount when SDMs are combined to form an overall metric, such as species richness (Grenié et al., 2020).

Estimating endemism is complex, regardless of the method or scenario, yielding large variability in results. This effect may be ascribed to the intrinsic nature of the metric, which aims to identify spatial concentrations of species with restricted distributions. In our experiment, we did not establish rules that determine the spatial concentration of species with restricted distributions, making endemism prediction more challenging (Hobohm & Tucker, 2014; Shipley & McGuire, 2023). It is important to note that in the real world, endemism may have other causes, aside from environmental determinants, such as historical evolutionary events (Heads, 2018; Hendriks et al., 2019; Nogueira et al., 2011). Despite the

equivalent predictive capacity of the tested methods, the USSE approach yields slightly superior and less dispersed results. Therefore, this approach in modeling endemism may represent a promising choice, capable of achieving comparable or even superior results than those of other methods.

The low sensitivity to sampling bias and the little dispersion of results of GDM make it a robust approach for predicting beta-diversity even using poorly sampled collections. Conversely, SCI yielded inferior results with large dispersion. The consistent success of GDM, even in scenarios of unfavorable sampling effort, may be attributed to the nature of the metric, which is naturally less influenced by sampling bias (Oliveira et al., 2016). In recent years, there has been a growing number of publications using the GDM method for predicting beta-diversity (Mokany et al., 2022), and our results underpin the relevance of this method. To better understand and explore the behavior of GDM in various contexts, such as the inclusion of multiple predictors, we suggest conducting controlled simulations, similar to what has been done with SDM methods (Fernandes et al., 2018; Meynard et al., 2019; Miller, 2014).

The experimental design we developed simulating species distribution scenarios is frequently employed in tests involving SDMs (Fernandes et al., 2018; Meynard et al., 2019; Miller, 2014). Here we expanded this approach to evaluate the effectiveness of other biodiversity estimation methods under multiple scenarios of species distribution and sampling efforts with varying degrees of prediction difficulty. Controlled simulations, as we have done in this study, are therefore an important tool to test biodiversity methods. In short, these tests can isolate confounding factors inherent to real-world data, enabling a robust assessment of biodiversity methods.

Conclusion

Our simulation approach has the potential to evaluate a wide range of methods and parameters for biodiversity, biogeography, and macroecology analyses, as it can help clarify the implications of methodological choices under various sampling and species distribution contexts. This type of assessment is crucial for improving the methods for conservation prioritization, management, and restoration planning, to which SDMs have been commonly applied (Banerjee et al., 2022; Swan et al., 2021), despite the demonstrated limitations of this method. Not only environmental prediction with USSE outperforms all other tested methods for estimating species richness in any modeled context, it also analyzes the entire biota, in contrast to conventional SDMs. Thus, the method introduced in our study is able to make better informed decisions about biodiversity distribution, especially in the tropics where sampling gaps are a prominent issue.

The escalating biodiversity crisis demands immediate and effective national and global conservation policies underpinned by sound scientific recommendations

(Secretariat of the Convention on Biological Diversity (SCBD), 2022). Therefore, scholars and decision-makers must strive to best overcome the limitations of sampling biases and modeling uncertainties, without delaying the bold conservation actions much needed. Although fieldwork and curation of biological collections remain indispensable for improving real-world biodiversity information (García-Roselló et al., 2023; Vargas et al., 2023), species distribution modeling, which is comparatively less time- and resource-intensive, can help advance both science and the design of sound policies in the short term. While long-term data physical collection efforts must continue, USSE methodology can be readily employed to update and even refine priority areas for conservation at the national level, potentially identifying under-sampled regions and at the same time facilitating the discovery of new areas of high biodiversity importance. Additionally, environmental impact studies focused on remote areas, such as the Brazilian government's recent announcement of oil exploration in the Amazon river estuary (EBC, 2023), could also benefit from our methodology since it can improve understanding and raise awareness of poorly sampled areas. In essence, the scientific community should embrace a pragmatic approach that balances the need for rigorous data collection with the urgency of implementing effective conservation measures. By combining traditional and innovative methods, we can bridge the gap between knowledge and action, helping to protect biodiversity worldwide.

Figure 1: **A:** environmental predictor variable (1st PCA axis); **B:** species richness measured directly from the simulated maps of species distribution under scenarios 25, 50, 75, 100; **C:** the accessibility map; and **D:** correlation between species richness measured directly from the simulated maps of species distribution under scenarios 25, 50, 75, and 100 and the accessibility map.

Figure 2: Pearson correlation (r) between the estimated biodiversity dimensions. **(A)** species richness, **(B)** endemism, and **(C)** beta-diversity) from each method under the modeled scenarios and those directly measured from the simulated maps of species distribution. Species Distribution Models (SDM); Spatial Interpolation (SI); Environmental Prediction (EP); Environmental Prediction with Uniform Sampling from Sampling Effort (USSE). Frequency from 100 replicas of each species distribution scenario. The USSE approach out performed the other methods in predicting species richness, and was similar to the other methods in estimating endemism and beta-diversity.

Figure 3: Linear regression between species richness estimates and sampling effort: **A:** Measured directly from the simulated maps of species distribution; **B:** estimated with hexagons; **C:** estimated using SDMs; **D:** estimated from spatial interpolation; **E:** estimated from environmental prediction; and **F:** estimated from environmental prediction with USSE. The USSE approach reduced the most the effects of collection bias in predicting species richness.

Figure 4: Linear regression between endemity estimates and sampling effort: **A:** measured directly from the simulated maps of species distribution; **B:** estimated with hexagons; **C:** estimated from spatial interpolation; **D:** estimated from environmental prediction; and **E:** estimated from environmental prediction with USSE. The USSE approach reduced the most the effects of collection bias in predicting endemity.

Figure 5: Linear regression between beta-diversity estimates and sampling effort: **A**: measured directly from the simulated maps of species distribution; **B**: estimated with hexagons; **C**: estimated from spatial interpolation; **D**: estimated from environmental prediction; and **E**: estimated from environmental prediction USSE.

Biosketch

Ubirajara Oliveira is a PhD in Zoology interested in theoretical, empirical and methodological aspects of biogeography. His current research includes studies on biogeography, macroecology, conservation, biodiversity models, environmental models and fire models.

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